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Mahul Tree: It's Significance in the Socio-Economic Life of the Tribes- A Case Study of Mayurbhanj District in Odisha

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Abstract

Mahua tree is known by the tribes in various names. The hill Kharias, the Bathudis, the Bhuyans calls it as Mahula Gachha in the district of Mayurbhanj. The Santhal and the Mundari speaking tribes call it as Matkam Dare or Matkam Daru9. In Bengali it is called Mahua tree. It is a medium size deciduous tree. The height of the tree is 16 to 20 meters. The Mahua plants take 10 or more years to becoming a flower bearing tree in the climate of Mayurbhanj. Most of the trees are found in the forest, Dahi or uplands and even in the paddy lands in Mayurbhanj. The tribes and other artisans did not cut the Mahua tree though it makes trouble to grow the corn in their field. According to them the flowers, fruits, leaves, wood as well as all the parts of the tree are directly or indirectly useful to them. The Kudmis an agrarian community who were recognized as tribes up to 1956 regarded the Mahul tree as a sacred tree and used it in auspicious rituals. During the marriage ceremony the bride is taken under the Mahul tree to perform customary rituals

Key words: Mahul Tree, Mahua, Odisha Tribes,

Odisha is proud of having her wealth in the form of tribal people because of its vast tribal population and their rich cultural heritage. The culture of Odisha owes its origin to tribal oriented customs and traditions¹. The early name of Odra, Kalinga and Utkala, which formed the modern state of Odisha, were named after the tribes in the hoary past². All through ages the tribes played important role for the socio-political and cultural progress of the state. The tribes mostly inhabit in the south-western and northern hilly regions of the state mainly in close proximity to forest. More than 50 percent of Odisha's tribal population is found in the undivided Koraput, Sundargarh, Fulbani and Mayurbhanj districts. The prominent tribes of Mayurbhanj are the *Santhals*, the *Kolhas*, the *Bhumijas*, the *Bathudis*, the *Bhuyans*,

the *Kharias*, the *Lodhas* and others³. The tribes have their distinct culture and customs. They are simple innocent and very shy in nature.

Most of the tribes of Eastern India used to live in an area made up by hills, valleys and forested tracts. It was a land moist tropical deciduous forest featured by tall trees rising up to forty meters. The tribes consider the forest as their home and hearth⁴. They have deep conviction even today that forest belongs to them. They have been demanding it as their ancestral property since the remote past. The *Kharia* tribes consider the whole forest as their rice pot. They think that god has created the forest for them to use it in deed and need. When the British government enacted laws to preserve forest in the tribal areas, they revolted against it. They express their crisis through the folk jhumar song.

Pat tuli niti niti Jhuli jhanti datan kathi
*Aj kene babui kare mana go uader man nain chhila jana*⁵.

The poor tribes were collecting leaves, firewood, fencing material and tooth-twigs from the forest. They were using the forest according to their own needs and will. But after the states control, they were astonished to see the gentleman in the forests who refused their entry.

The close intimacy among the plants, the animals and the people was found in the early history of the people. The plants like the *Asan*, *Kendu*, *Mahul*, *Chara*, *Dha*, *Bela*, *Anala*, *Harida*, *Bahada*, *Bambo* and others are popular plants that utilized by the tribes. Among all the trees the tribes regard much to *Mahul* tree as the protector of their life. There is a saying among the tribes is that “Heaven is where there is *Mahua* tree and hell is where there is no *Mahua* tree to make wine”⁶.

There is a myth among the *Santhals* of Ayodhya Hill of West-Bengal regarding the origin of *Mahul* tree. Once upon a time a Sadhu was living in Ayadhya Hill. There was a tiger, a bear and a *moyna* bird in his *Ashram*. One day the Sadhu expired in natural death due to old age. The *Santhals* assembled for cremation. The dead body was placed on the pyre for burning. Suddenly the tiger, bear and the *moyna* jumped into the fire. The *Santhals* astonished and saw the affection of man and animals⁷.

One day morning an aged person went to the forest for the collection for *sal* leaves and edible tubers. Suddenly he saw a new variety of flowers on the ground and observed the uncommon variety of tree with its branches and green leaves. Then he recalled the spot, that five years before where pyre was made for

In the month of *Magha* the tribes of Mayurbhanj are observed *Maghe* festival. It is a thank giving festival to the gods and goddess for last year good harvest and also welcome for the beginning next year cultivation. In the meanwhile they pray for growing their natural resources in the forest in shape of green leaves beautiful flowers and fruits. The *Santhals* and other tribes worship their gods and goddess in the high hills. The tribes of Uparbhag observe Maghpudi festival on the *Thakurani* hill near Mangadh village. The Oriya speaking tribes like the *Bathudis* , the *Bhuyans* and others gathered at Bangriposi Ghati to worship Maa Dwarsuni in the month of Magh. In the Majhalbhag Pragana the tribes gathered on the *Thakurini* hill to worship Maa Sataputuli. They believe that the seven sisters are worshiped on that occasion to fulfill their desire¹².

In the month of *Falguna Salipuja*, *Jahirapuja* and *Garampuja* are observed in each and every tribal village. During this *puja Sal* and *Mahul* flowers are offered to their deity then collect and used these flowers. The *Mahul* tree has helped a lot during the time of famine which the district faced very often. At that time they were taking the *Mahul* paste, fried and boiled *Mahul* to pass the sad days. That is why the tribes call *Maul* tree as their life saving tree. They believe that their forefather have been preserving the *Mahul* trees for them since a remote past. The *santhals* sing *Dahar* song as follows:

<i>Dare Dare Khan Jata Dare Khan</i>	<i>Matkam Dare Da Damange.</i>
<i>Rengej Tetang Te Baban Tahen</i>	<i>Matkam Lathe tiki Ata Kateb Jam Ge.</i>
<i>Jatan Dahayaba Matkam Dare</i>	<i>Agil Haplam Kaka Rakha Daha Akad.</i> ¹³

The *Mahul* trees are most valuable tree of tribal society. It provides work to them in summer when there was no agricultural operation. It also provides delicious food to them. There will be no shortage of food if there are *Mahul* trees. Their predecessors have gifted these trees. So it is the high time to preserve and take care of the *Mahul* tree.

Mhaul tree is the only tree which helped the tribes for their economic development. During the month of *Falgun* and *Chaitra* they do not fear the summer hit and go out to collect *Mahul* flowers from their fields. The landless tribes go to deep forest for collection of *Mahua* flowers. All the flowers fall at night and in the early morning under the tree. The earth is not visible at that time. After collecting huge amount of *Mahuls* the tribal women return home with a basketful flower on her head. Their bodies become wet by the sweet juice of *Mahua* flowers. At that time the Santhals sing *Dahar* song as follows-

*Sarjam Gele Ha Matkambaha Matkam Baha
Disampala Ha Hula Chamka
Santhal, Lalka, Munda, Mahele, Kunbi Eman*

*Muluh Banga Ha Baha Banga,
Kherwar Kaka Taken Kan ,
Matkam Rasa Ha Sarabara.*

This song reveals that after the worship of flowers or *Baha Banga*, the *Santhals*, the *Kolhas*, the *Mundas*, the *Mahali*, the *Kudmis* and other tribes collect *Mahul* flowers. At that time there was a hue and cry all over the tribal land. The sweet juice of the flower drops from their head.

The tribal children are fond of chewing sweet juice of *Mahua* flower. They make *tattoos* in their body by using its juice and the remaining ashes of half burnt leaves. Some of them boils *Mahul* juice and sun-dried rice in the field and enjoy them.¹⁴

Mahuls are dried in the backyard or front-yard of their house. The tribes' sale the dry flowers in their local Market. Some of the tribes store the flowers to get high amount of money or to meet the need when there would be the scarcity of food. A few of them know the art of making liquor from *Mahul* flower. It is called *Mahuli* by the *Odia* speaking tribes as it prepared from *Mahul* flowers. The *Kolhas*, *Santhals* and other tribes call it *parua*. They are selling the liquor in the Market, cock-pit and in their villages. They maintain their family by earning the amount from the liquor. The tribes of Mayurbhanj dance whole the night taking *Mahuli* or *parua* with abundant joy without any inhabitation.¹⁵

After giving flowers the *Mahul* tree bears fruits in all and every branches of it. The *Mahul* fruits are called *Kachada* in the district of Mayurbhanj. The *Kolhas* and *Santhals* call it as *Kuindi*. Its colour is always green. The tribes prepare testy curry from the green *Mahul* fruits. They have recognized the particular tree whose fruits are used for curry. The ripe fruit is very sweet. The bats, parrots and some other birds used to take the cover part of the fruits. The green part of the fruit is a delicious food of the cattle and goats. There are seeds in the inner portion of the *Mahul* fruits. The tribes collect the seeds of *Mhaul* fruits and after removing the hard cover they dried them. They use stones for removing the cover. They get a handsome amount of money selling the dried seeds. Some tribes used to exert oil from the seeds. They were making *Jant* by two big logs to exert oil. But it was a very difficult process and required more man power. Presently Oil exerting machine are used everywhere. The tribes cook their food, prepare cakes and smear *Kachada* oil on their body before bath. This oil keeps their body healthy, smooth and clean.¹⁶

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After exerting oil the extra oil less part is called cake. It is used as natural manure. This manure does not affect the soil or its fertility. It helps the paddy to grow up and avoid the appearance of insects. The tribes also apply it in their nearby stream to catch fishes. The fishes are intoxicated by the mixture of water and cakes of *Mahua* seeds by which they easily catch them without net. Taking these fishes do not make harmful in their body. The tribes collect the dry *Mahul* leaves to boil paddy, rice and also prepare curry. The dry branches and trunk of the tree are used for fuel. The *Mahul* wood as fuel burn well. The farmers during his work in the field take breakfast and must have take rest under the *Mahul* tree.¹⁷

Thus *Mahul* trees are most valuable as well as sacred trees of the tribes of Mayurbhanj in particular and Odisha in general. It is valuable on the ground that all the parts including its flower, fruits and seeds are highly profitable for them. It is sacred because they worship it along with the sal tree in their *Jahira* or the community place of worship. In *Saleipuja* they offer *sal* as well as *Mahul* flowers to propitiate their gods and goddess. They have so much intimacy with the *Mahul* tree is that they buried the dead body of the dead baby and pray her to take care as mother. In this way the *Mahul* trees play significant role in the socio-economic life of the tribes.

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8. *Ibid*
9. The author interviewed Sri Binod Naik an aged man of 70 years and also a prominent scholar of Tribal culture and collected the data on 14.01.2019.

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10. This marriage song is collected from Smt. Babita Kailayar Mohanta, a famous Jhumar singer of Rairangpur on 18.01.2019.
11. The author has collected the fact from Sri Baidhar Murmu of Rayan village of Bangriposi Block in the district of Mayurbhanj on 14.01.2019.
12. This *Daher* song of the Santhals is collected from Sri Soner Sing Hansdah, a learned school teacher of Rayan village of Bangriposi Block in the district of Mayurbhanj on 14.01.2019.
13. *Ibid.*
14. Sri Binod Naik, *op.cit.*
15. Baidhar Murmu, *op.cit.*
16. The author made a visit to the village Sankhabhanja of Saraskana Block and met Sri Kameswar Singh on 01-01-2019.
17. *Ibid.*